

LESSONS LEARNED IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A
MULTIVARIABLE CONTROL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

A primary objective of the STOL and Maneuver Technology Demonstrator (S/MTD) program is the development of an Integrated Flight/Propulsion Control (IFPC) system. The use of modern multivariable control theory was required for this program, but in implementation a combined classical and multivariable design approach has been found to be the most efficient. The architecture defined by the multivariable approach was chosen for some control modes and by the classical approach for others. The problems overcome in realizing an effective and practical implementation are discussed. Finally, some recommendations for control system research are presented.

INTRODUCTION

The S/MTD program was structured to investigate, develop and validate through analysis, experiment and flight test, four specific technologies related to providing current and future high performance fighters with both STOL capability and enhanced combat mission performance. These technologies are:

- o Two-dimensional thrust vectoring and reversing exhaust nozzle
- o Integrated flight/propulsion control (IFPC) system
- o Pilot Vehicle Interface (PVI)
- o Rough/soft field landing gear

These technologies have been incorporated into a two-place F-15B together with all-moving canard surfaces (see Figure 1).

The overriding requirement of the IFPC system was stated to be "capable of functionally integrating all aspects of flight, engine, and nozzle control including aerodynamic control surfaces, engine thrust, thrust vectoring, thrust reversing and differential efflux modulation, control and stability augmentation, high lift system, steering and braking". The intent was to convey the understanding that integration was an objective of the demonstration program, not just a means to achieve mission requirements. The IFPC system was required to provide "good inner-loop stability and positive manual control

in all axes of the air vehicle throughout its intended operating envelope both in flight and on the ground (satisfying the intent of MIL-F-8785C)". This subjective requirement was intended to convey that we were seeking good flying qualities over the whole envelope guided more by the intent than the letter of the specification. This recognizes that, while the intent is to provide flying qualities clearly adequate for the mission, the letter of the specification is no guarantee. In addition, the requirement for 'positive manual control' was intended to preclude consideration of automatic landing systems, for instance. One flying qualities requirement that was explicitly called out in the Statement of Work was to minimize time delay, i.e., lag in aircraft response to pilot control input. Although the importance of time delay is more widely accepted now, it still should be an explicit, hard requirement in any control system to be designed for any precise task, regardless of the method of design or implementation.

The system was required to be designed to meet the intent of MIL-F-9490D with the stability margins of MIL-F-9490D as design goals, followed by: "Such single-input/single-output parameters may be too restrictive or too lenient for different aspects of the IFPC system in achieving the desired compromise between stability and performance. The contractor shall analyze and document deviations from the MIL-F-9490D requirements". This was, therefore, a requirement to validate or correct the 6db gain margin and 45° phase margin for such a complex system.

Figure 1. S/MTD Configuration

Specific flight control modes were required with the rationale: "In order to provide the ability to assess task performance and minimize pilot workload in the flight vehicle, the integrated system shall also provide the flexibility to permit inflight selection of mission task oriented control modes as determined by analysis and simulation. Mode switching transients shall not produce unsafe aircraft responses. As a minimum, the following modes are required:

Aerodynamic	Propulsive	Landing Gear
• Stabilator *	• Gross Thrust	• Main Gear Brakes *
• Canard *	• Primary Jet Vectoring — Pitch — Roll	• Nose Gear Steering
• Aileron *		
• Flaperon *	• Rotating Vane Vectoring — Pitch — Roll — Yaw — Reversing	
• Rudder		
• Speedbrake		

* Both collective and differential

Figure 2. Available Control Effectors

A CONVENTIONAL mode shall be designed for satisfactory performance over the flight test envelope, including conventional landing, without the use of the added technologies. This mode will serve as a baseline for performance evaluation and as a backup in the event of multiple failure of the new technology components.

A STOL mode shall be designed to provide precise manual control of flight path trajectory, airspeed and aircraft attitudes. The integrated control system and other technologies shall be combined to provide short field performance in weather and poor visibility. The purpose of this mode is to minimize pilot workload during precise manual landings, high reverse thrust ground operations and maximum performance takeoffs.

A CRUISE mode shall be designed to enhance normal up-and-away and cruise task performance, with and without external stores. The purpose of this mode is to use the integrated control system and other technologies to optimize appropriate measures of merit representing an improvement over the cruise capability of the baseline aircraft.

A COMBAT mode shall be designed to enhance up-and-away maneuverability, with and without external stores. The purpose of this mode is to use the integrated control system and other technologies to optimize appropriate measures of merit representing an improvement over the combat maneuvering or weapon delivery performance of the baseline aircraft".

The different modes were called out in this form for technology demonstration purposes, with general guidance as to the intent of each mode. Once the benefits of the technologies have been identified, it was expected that they would be implemented differently in any production application.

All the bidders on the S/MTD contract were strongly encouraged to use multivariable control theory, although it was not expressed as an absolute requirement. With integration as a program objective, there was some uncertainty that a classical approach would optimize use of all the available effectors (Figure 2). At the same time, there was no desire to commit to a totally multivariable design approach. The purpose of this paper is to document the fallout

of this approach. The paper is written from the perspective of the government and the prime contractor managers responsible for the development of the S/MTD control system. Before proceeding, we should define what is meant by the terms 'classical and multivariable design approach' for the purposes of this discussion.

In simple terms, a classical design develops in a step by step process to satisfy textbook modal requirements in the military flying qualities specification with proportional feedback and tailor outer-loop characteristics with integral terms (illustrated conceptually in Figure 3). Second order effects such as adverse coupling are eliminated with crossfeed, but details of these requirements are frequently a fallout as the design progresses. A significant advantage is the insight into the system that is provided by the process itself of adding complexity in discrete steps to enhance system performance. On the other hand, the result is dependent on the fidelity of the plant model to an unknown extent and there is frequently not a well-defined end to the process (other than schedule).

- o No prefilter
- o Gains selected to provide desired flying qualities

Figure 3. Classical Design Philosophy

Longitudinal flying qualities specifications for the STOL Landing and STOL Takeoff modes are as follows:

- Positive AOA stability.
- Neutral airspeed stability.
- Constant and uniform stick force per AOA below 16° AOA.
- Increased stick force per AOA above 16° AOA.
- Canard is scheduled vs. AOA for static stability augmentation and performance optimization. Perturbations about the trim schedule may be used during maneuvering if this improves control characteristics or reduces hydraulic flow demand while providing the required aircraft response.
- Flaperons or ailerons and flaperons will be used for direct lift only if required to meet these design guidelines.
- A second order pitch response to stick input is desired. Preferred equivalent system transfer functions are given below:

$$\frac{\alpha}{\text{Stick}} = \frac{G[w_s^2/(n/\alpha)](v/g)}{s^2 + 2\zeta_w w_s s + w_s^2} \frac{-T_d s}{e} \quad \frac{\text{deg}}{\text{in}}$$

$$\frac{q}{\text{Stick}} = \frac{G w_s^2 [((v/g)/(n/\alpha)) s + 1]}{s^2 + 2\zeta_w w_s s + w_s^2} \frac{-T_d s}{e} \quad \frac{\text{deg/sec}}{\text{in}}$$

$$\frac{u}{\text{Stick}} = 0 \quad \frac{\text{ft/sec}}{\text{in}}$$

$$n/\alpha = \frac{-Z\alpha}{g} \quad \frac{\text{g/rad}}{\text{g}}$$

$0.6 \leq \zeta_w \leq 0.8$
 $w_s \geq 2.0 \text{ rad/sec}$

For uniform pitch acceleration, $[w_s^2/(n/\alpha)](v/g) = 7.5$

$G = \text{Stick Gain} = 2.0 \text{ deg/sec/in}$

Above 16 deg AOA, the stick gain should decrease ($G = \text{TBD}$)

Stick Gradient = 6 lb/in

$T_d = \text{Time Delay} < 100 \text{ milliseconds}$.

The actual aircraft response should follow the above transfer functions over the frequency range of 0.5 to 20 rad/sec.

- $W_{BW} > 3 \frac{\text{rad}}{\text{sec}}$ (STI bandwidth criterion)
- A first order velocity response to throttle input is desired. The preferred equivalent system transfer function is given below:

$$\frac{u}{\text{Throttle}} = \frac{G a}{s + a} \frac{-T_d s}{e} \quad \frac{\text{ft/sec}}{\text{deg}}$$

$$G = 5 \frac{\text{ft/sec}}{\text{deg}}$$

$$0.1 \leq a \leq 0.2 \text{ rad/sec}$$

$$T_d \leq 150 \text{ milliseconds}$$

Steady state pitch rate and flight path rate for a throttle input shall be zero. The aircraft load factor should remain in trim.

Transient pitch rate for a positive throttle input shall be zero or positive; transient flight path rate shall be positive.

AOA must change with airspeed to meet the pitch rate and flight path rate requirement. Transient AOA for a positive throttle input shall not be positive.

The actual aircraft response should follow the above transfer function over the frequency range of 0.05 to 5 rad/sec.

The control system velocity damping feedback should not restrict steady-state throttle/vane authority.

Airspeed oscillations ("pulsing") should not occur as the result of throttle or stick inputs.

Figure 6. STOL Mode Design Requirements

plant with conventional controls to satisfy conventional requirements so that the multivariable approach could provide no benefits.

For the CRUISE and COMBAT modes, the lateral and directional requirements are conventional so that the classical design approach was again chosen. Additional requirements, however, were imposed on the longitudinal axis. Canard deflection and nozzle vector angle were coordinated to minimize steady-state drag at 1g in the CRUISE mode and at elevated load factors in the COMBAT mode, in addition to their use for short-term pitch control. In these cases, the benefits of the multivariable approach, guaranteeing stability and robustness, made it the one of choice. The compensator order could be reduced to a practical proportional plus integral structure without significant degradation in stability margin. A more significant effect of compensator order reduction is deviation from the ideal form of the compensated plant, which is discussed later.

Requirements for the STOL mode (Figure 6) included decoupling airspeed from the pitch axis in order to provide the precision for minimizing touchdown dispersion. High bandwidth augmentation of airspeed stability is achieved because of the high response rates of the reverser vanes compared with changing thrust by means of engine speed. Airspeed is fed back to vane deflections with different schedules top and bottom to give zero pitching moment. Throttle deflection then commands airspeed. With this effective speed hold, pitch rate command by the stick becomes flight path angle rate command. With additional requirements as in Figure 6, the multivariable approach was the clear choice. In this case, control system performance was measured by the amount of cross coupling. This showed a measurable increase as the order of the compensator was reduced from fifth order. Piloted simulation was required to verify that a second-order compensator was satisfactory to the pilot. The final STOL longitudinal control laws are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. STOL Landing Pitch Axis Control Laws and Response Characteristics

Initially, only conventional lateral and directional requirements were considered for the STOL modes. After the choice of a classical design had been made, piloted simulations indicated that the crosswind landing imposed an additional requirement. This led to the implementation of direct sideforce (differential canard plus rudder deflection) as a function of rudder pedal input. This can now easily be formulated as a requirement to be included in the multivariable design approach, but in practice it was a fallout as the classical design progressed.

LESSONS LEARNED

The first result is not really a surprise. For the modes or axes that had only conventional controls/requirements, the multivariable design technique did not offer any benefit. The choices by mode and axis are shown in Figure 8.

**Combination Of Multivariable And Classical Analysis
Methods Used To Design Control Laws**

	Honeywell LQG/LTR Analysis	MCAIR Classical Analysis
Longitudinal		
CONV		X
CRUISE/COMBAT	X	
STOL-LAND	X	
STOL-TOA	X	
STOL-GH		X
Lateral/Directional		
CONV		X
CRUISE/COMBAT		X
STOL-LAND		X
STOL-TOA		X
STOL-GH		X
Thrust		
CONV		X
CRUISE/COMBAT		X
STOL-LAND	X	
STOL-TOA		X
STOL-GH		X

Figure 8. Choices of Design Approach

An aspect of the development that gave totally unexpected benefits was the synergism of the parallel design process for the unconventional modes. One of the critical areas of multivariable control theory is to establish all the design requirements as the starting point. A full performance design is then synthesized to satisfy them. The classical approach addresses the requirements individually, in principle, although an experienced designer uses his past experience to approach the final solution efficiently. Both McAir and Honeywell used experienced control system designers. Even so, the classical McAir design benefitted from knowledge of the performance attainable by the multivariable design. Simultaneously, the Honeywell design simplified the high-order compensator of the full-performance design aided by the knowledge of the performance attainable with the simpler formulations of the classical design. The result, from the management perspective, was convergence on an optimum balance of performance and complexity (depicted in Figure 9).

Figure 9. Convergence of Parallel Design Process

The desire was to utilize multivariable control theory to the extent possible; however, there was concern as to the ability to physically implement a control law set derived using both those techniques. It was decided to do the dual development of the control laws using both the classical and modern methods, and compare the results prior to choosing the set to be programmed. As described above, the two methods essentially start from the opposite positions with respect to both performance and complexity, and evolve toward the same point, as shown in Figure 9. The use of the flight simulator to compare the flying qualities obtained with each set aided in both the evolution and in the comparison. Considering the similarity of the resulting two sets of control laws, the consensus was that both the speed and accuracy of this evolutionary process, regardless of the method

being used, depended more on the capability of the individual doing the work than on the process itself. In addition, the combined approach was more efficient than either by itself for the modes or axes with more than conventional requirements.

While the contract Statement of Work called out compliance with the intent of MIL-F-8785C and MIL-F-9490D, it was recognized that strict compliance with those specifications was not sufficient to assure optimum flying qualities. A group of "second tier" flying qualities criteria was used during the development of the control laws to improve the tactical capability (e.g. Reference 7). This included the use at the outset of the program of a "generic" simulation to define the criteria for the approach and rollout. While none of the requirements of the primary specifications were violated by the final results, the concept of keeping each of the parameters in the middle of the specification envelope was abandoned in favor of obtaining pilot acceptance of the overall results. Pilot comments from the flight test program to date have indicated that not only does the airplane provide Level 1 flying qualities throughout the envelope, but the airplane "flies more like an airplane than any past vehicle using a fly-by-wire system" that the pilots have flown.

It is important that this result is interpreted correctly. MIL-F-8785C requirements are to be applied to "equivalent system" representations of the actual aircraft dynamics, expressed in terms of classical second-order modal responses. What is defined, however, is a family of response characteristics. Initial piloted simulation yielded Level 2 ratings for target tracking in the CONVENTIONAL and COMBAT modes, and Reference 7 documents how the second-tier criteria were used to reformulate a different second-order pitch rate response that received Level 1 ratings. In the final implementation, however, there are slight differences between the two modes. Figure 10 contains the pitch rate frequency responses of the two modes - the COMBAT mode shows slightly more deviation from a pure second-order response. This difference has proven to be significant to the pilots, average pilot ratings for fine target tracking have been Cooper-Harper ratings of 2 for the CONVENTIONAL mode and 3 for COMBAT mode. [For the record, the COMBAT mode is improved overall by better target acquisition because of the contribution of pitch vectoring].

Part of this difference came from the implementation of structural filters. The aeroservoelastic analysis was being done by McAir simultaneously with the control law development. Addition of the effect of the structural filters to the control laws developed by the multivariable was much more difficult to perform than the similar effort being done on the balance of the system, since the inclusion of those effects impacted the design of the prefilters used to shape the response to the pilot commands. A late change in filter characteristics was thought to

a. CONVENTIONAL mode

Figure 10. Pitch Rate Response Characteristics

be a small impact, but may have contributed to the above COMBAT mode tracking characteristic. Another possible cause has also been discussed - compensator order reduction which, in this case, gave a second-order (proportional plus integral) compensator. A more complex regulated variable would also have been an option to improve the responses. More iterations could have been performed with the multivariable synthesis to improve the flying qualities. In reality, a production development program may or may not pay for an improvement in a flying qualities range predicted to be Level 1 (i.e., 'satisfactory without improvement' by definition). For the S/MTD program, time constraints precluded this further development.

One of the comparisons to be made when assessing two methodologies is the ease of modifying the results or, if necessary, the ease of correcting deficiencies. In this respect, the insight into the design process provided by the classical method of control law development/analysis has a distinct advantage over the multivariable techniques. For example,

b. COMBAT mode

Figure 10. Pitch Rate Response Characteristics

during the early flight testing of the CONVENTIONAL mode, it was discovered that the system damping was lower than desirable at low altitude, high speed flight conditions. While the causes and fixes for the condition were being investigated, a simple patch to the software was installed, changing the feedback gains and providing sufficient damping to continue the flight test program. Had those particular control laws been developed using the modern method, a complete analysis of the system would have been required to define the changes required to improve the flying qualities. This is further support for the conclusion that multivariable theory is not warranted for a conventional design problem. The converse is probably also true - such a problem in one of the complex modes might not be so amenable to a simple fix.

As stated earlier, one of the design goals was to meet the stability requirements of MIL-F-9490D, or to define recommended changes to the criteria. The design used the 6 db gain and 45 deg. phase limits as total loop design requirements. The flight test problem mentioned above was manifested first by the pilots

complaining about the pitch axis "ringing". In other words, aircraft response to the normal flight test stick inputs did not damp out as expected. Analysis of the flight test data revealed that the gain margin had decreased to approximately 3 db. The temporary fix that restored damping also restored gain margin to 6 db and gave flying qualities satisfactory for completion of the flight test. The S/MTD project has validated MIL-F-9490D requirements for overall loop gain and phase margin. Although not addressed in this paper, the validation also applies to the 8 db requirement at structural frequencies.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

For control system problems which are purely conventional, there is no benefit to the use of multivariable theory, while the classical design process provides better insight into the system. For complex systems or unconventional requirements, a combined classical and multivariable design approach gives the best convergence to the optimum trade-off of complexity for performance.

Evaluation of military specifications was an objective of the S/MTD program. MIL-F-9490D has been used as a design requirement for multivariable control system design and validated by flight test. The problems of using MIL-F-8785C as a flying qualities design requirement are independent of whether a classical or a multivariable design technique is being used. Second tier criteria (as contained in the MIL-Standard to replace MIL-F-8785C) are necessary to produce satisfactory flying qualities for precision tasks such as fine tracking. The implication of MIL-F-8785C, that "pure" second order modal responses are best, should be stated as an explicit design requirement. The "full-performance" multivariable solution gives a pure response by definition. This is affected, however, by simplifications in the formulation and by changes in the plant characteristics. It is normal to assess the robustness of the design system stability in the face of plant uncertainty. It would be beneficial to conduct research into techniques for ensuring an analogous robustness with respect to purity of response.

As stated previously, the authors concur that most specifications follow the development of new technologies, and will prevent repeating past errors. Significant research is being conducted at all times into criteria for the development of both the control laws and the computers in which they will reside. Since both references 2 and 3 were derived from flight experience with less complex flight control systems, they provide good foundations for how the flying qualities should evolve, but do not consider some of the higher order effects seen with newer systems. The development of the S/MTD control laws focused on the pilots' opinion of the achieved characteristics, and then assessed the criteria in terms of which of the primary or secondary criteria was

more apropos for a given task. Two examples are the requirements for the high performance approach and the tight tracking during air-to-air combat. In both cases, the requirements of reference 2 provided handling qualities ratings of Level 2 if they were not modified by task-oriented considerations. This was particularly interesting in the difference in requirements which resulted in Level 1 ratings for the gross acquisition task as compared to the later tight tracking task. It is recommended that consideration of such newly published criteria be included in the specification of the control law development.

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